

**REFLECTION OF NATIONAL MENTALITY IN PROVERBS WITH
SOMATIC COMPOSITION IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES
THROUGH THE HEAD LEXEME**

Akbaraliyeva Khurshida Shavkatjon kizi

National University of Uzbekistan scientific researcher

akbaraliyevakhurshida315@gmail.com

+998990618349

Abstract. This article examines the national-cultural and universal features of proverbs in both languages with the participation of the “head” somatism in Uzbek and English, and presents the conclusions of famous writers and scientists in their work on proverbs, as well as the role and significance of proverbs in human life. When we compared proverbs in different languages, we identified differences and similarities between them.

Keywords: paremia, proverb, concept, grammar, comparison, hand.

INTRODUCTION

Somatic proverbs are a type of proverb that uses body parts or body functions as metaphors to convey a certain message or moral lesson. In this conceptual analysis, we will consider the components of somatic proverbs in Uzbek and English. The conceptual analysis of somatic proverbs uses body parts such as the head, heart, and feet to express the concepts and meanings based on the decomposition of the components of the proverb.

The paremiological fund has attracted researchers since ancient times, because it reflects the experience and wisdom of people, life situations, as well as stereotypes of certain behaviors. A very important part of the paremiological system of any folk world picture are “cultural codes”, the national specifics of which are not yet fully understood.

Somatisms represent concepts and relationships that are necessary in any human society, without which it is difficult to imagine human speech, somatic words are characterized by a rapid use of words and developed polysemy. Somatisms are an

integral system designed to define a certain composition of lexical units.

Somatic proverbs also include the concept phenomenon. In recent years, through it, the study of units that form semantic connections on the basis of concepts has become widespread in Uzbek linguistics. A concept is a unit of memory, knowledge, a picture of the world manifested in language and speech.

Let us also talk about the “concept”.

“Concept (lat. *conseptus* “concept”. S. Askaldov’s term).

1. Cognitive linguist: a unit of information system reflecting the mental and spiritual state of human consciousness, its knowledge and experience.

2. Linguoculturology: a unit of collective consciousness, which has a mental nature and linguistic expression, and is distinguished by its ethnocultural character.

3. In psycholinguistics: a mobile perceptual-cognitive-affective structure that arises in the cognitive and communicative activities of a person, subject to the laws of his psyche.

The problem of “concept” is one of the central problems of the anthropocentric paradigm. The essence of the concept, its types and relationship to language units have been widely covered in research.

As is known, concepts in linguistics are expressed mainly through lexical and lexical-phraseological units. In recent years, theoretical views and research on syntactic concepts have emerged.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS.

In the process of analyzing this article, the methods of logicity, historicity, consistency and objectivity of scientific knowledge were widely used. A brief analysis of the national-cultural and universal characteristics of proverbs in English and Uzbek was conducted. The book “Dictionary of American Proverbs” by G.L. Permyakov, “Fundamentals of Structural Paremiology” by Meider, Kingsburg, Harder was designated as a methodological source.

RESEARCH AND SCIENTIFIC RESULTS.

Although there are hundreds of English proverbs today, we used several

English proverbs about love in our research to express them through the lexeme of the heart. We considered these English proverbs to be the most suitable way for those interested in the culture of the English people to know their culture. As a result of our studies, it is precisely through the heart that proverbs about self-love, family love, and lost love are formed. In English proverbs, the *proverb* “*Never put off until tomorrow what you can do today*” is used to express the idea concisely and clearly. The proverb “*Don’t put off until tomorrow what you can do today*” is cited.

English proverbs are a collection of catchy words that tell the truth or give advice. These proverbs are usually used in conversation, and many of them are taken from old literature, songs, unique moments in history, or from great philosophers and great grandparents. Often, not every proverb is translated directly (literally) and is often used figuratively. We can cite one of the American proverbs used in its true sense: “Strike while the iron is hot” (Temirni qizig‘ida bos).

This word was literally said by blacksmiths (metalworkers), who meant to hit the iron with a hammer when it was hot. Here is an example of a proverb used figuratively: “*Seize opportunities as they arise*” or take advantage of the opportunity when it comes, it comes in the following meaning.

In the proverbs in which the lexeme “*head*” is present in the Uzbek and English linguistic picture of the world, it is used in the meanings of being a leader related to human abilities, leading other people. In family relationships, proverbs with a bosh component make the man the head of the family, and this is certainly symbolic. For example: “The husband is the head, the wife is the neck”. This proverb is talking about the process of a couple related to ancient morality, culture and human feelings.

The study of somatic proverbs falls within the broader field of paremiology, the study of idioms and other forms of traditional speech and proverbs. Wolfgang Mieder is a renowned paremiologist who has studied proverbs, idioms, and their cultural significance, and the use of body-related idioms and expressions in different cultural contexts. He has studied the use of somatic proverbs in different languages and cultures. Alan Dundes is a prominent folklorist who has written extensively on

folktales, including proverbs. His work often examines the cultural and symbolic aspects of proverbs and the use of body imagery in them. Somatic proverb theory emphasizes the rich cultural tapestry of human language. It emphasizes the importance of understanding the cultural and metaphorical context. In interpreting and appreciating these expressions, societies perceive and express key aspects of human experience, as they offer valuable insights into how to act.

1. *“Don’t lose your head”*. This proverb advises restraint, self-control. It emphasizes the importance of not panicking in difficult situations.

2. *“Keep your head above water”*. This proverb encourages people to manage their affairs even when faced with responsibility and difficulties. It means maintaining control and stability during difficult times.

3. *“Get your head out of the clouds”* This proverb advises someone to stop being too idealistic when focusing on goals and practical matters. It emphasizes the need to focus on the basics.

4. *“Bang your head against a brick wall”*. This proverb describes the futility of trying hard to achieve something when it seems impossible or futile. It shows the need to reconsider one’s approach.

The examples of proverbs continue to illustrate how the word “head” is used through metaphors in idiomatic expressions to convey a wide range of meanings and lessons. They are about wisdom, decision-making, avoidance, responsibility, leadership, and problem-solving. Proverbs are an invaluable tool for providing practical wisdom that encompasses cultural and data-driven insights, human behavior, and societal norms. When we compare these proverbs, we can see that Uzbek and English folk proverbs convey similar wisdom related to cooperation, calmness, rationality, and understanding complexity. While the common words and cultural contexts in these proverbs may differ, their underlying theme is the embodiment of human experience and values. In both languages, proverbs with the somatic component *“head”* use metaphorically different expressions and metaphors, using them to convey similar ideas. This shows the richness of idiomatic expressions in

each language. The specific vocabulary and context of proverbs can reflect cultural values and norms. If the main messages are similar, the relevant cultural contexts in which proverbs are used may be more related and relevant to each other. Proverbs often rely on language-specific features, such as linguistic concepts and wordplay, which makes direct translations difficult. This leads to differences in the pronunciation and structure of similar proverbs in different languages. Semantic analysis of somatic proverbs with the head component in Uzbek:

1. *“Ajral kelsa jahona, bosh og‘rig‘i bo‘lmas bahona”*. The semantic analysis of this proverb is based on the religious understanding that death does not have a specific, fixed time, it always comes unexpectedly.

2. *“Fikrli odam bosh bo‘lur, fikrsiz odam tosh bo‘lur”* va *“Bosh bo‘lmasa – gavda losh”*. Both proverbs mean that if people do not have knowledge in their heads, they will not be useful, the second proverb "lost" means only "flesh" without any knowledge.

3. *“Ayron – osh bo‘lmas ekan, nodon bosh bo‘lmas”*. *“Ignorant”* is a word in a broad sense and is used to refer to those who have such vices as stupid, foul-mouthed, lazy, boastful, ignorant, selfish, etc.

4. *“Bosh yorilsa bo‘rk ichida, qo‘l sinsa yeng ichida”*. This proverb refers to keeping a secret, and is more commonly used when one is wounded or disabled in battle and should not tell the enemy anything at all.

Cross analysis of Uzbek and English folk proverbs with the lexeme *“head”*:

№	Ingliz xalq maqollari	O‘zbek xalq maqollari
1.	Fish begins to stink at the head	Baliq boshidan sasiydi
2.	Better to be the head of a dog than the tail of a lion	Ho‘kuzning oyog‘i bo‘lguncha. Buzoqning boshi bo‘l. Beshning boshi bo‘lguncha Oltining oyog‘i bo‘l.
3.	Two heads are better than one	Bitta bosh yaxshi,

		Ikkitasi undanda yaxshi.
4.	A still tongue makes a wise head.	Izzat tilasang ko‘p dema, Sihat tilasang – ko‘p yema.
5.	Uneasy lies the head that wears a crown	Qari bilganni pari bilmaydi.
6.	Uneasy lies the head that wears a crown.	Boylar ham yig‘laydilar.
7.	Give your food to the people and they will pat your head.	Elga bersang go‘shingni, Erlar silar boshingni. Itga bersang oshingni, Itlar g‘ajir boshigni.

The English proverb “*Fish begins to stink at the head*” is pronounced similarly to the Uzbek proverb, and its alternative, “*Baliq boshidan sasiydi*” is equally popular in both cultures. It is an old proverb that has been used for centuries to express a situation where the leader of a group or organization is responsible for the corruption or incompetence of the entire group. The proverb suggests that if the leader of the group is corrupt or does not do his job properly, this will ultimately lead to the downfall of the entire group.

The proverb is a warning about the importance of having strong, honest, and competent leaders in any group or organization. If the leader is corrupt or incompetent, this will eventually lead to a situation where the entire organization begins to suffer and lose its effectiveness. In other words, if the head is rotten, the rest of the body will follow.

This wisdom also reminds us that those at the top of an organization are ultimately responsible for their actions and decisions, and that if they fail to lead properly, they should be held accountable. Leaders must do their job properly, or the organization will suffer.

“Better the head of a dog than the tail of a lion” – Another ancient proverb says the same thing more clearly: “Better be the head of the yeomanry than the tail of the

gentry”.

“Two heads are better than one”. It is better to consult with someone else before making an important decision.

“A still tongue makes a wise head” – You learn more by listening to others than by speaking yourself.

“You cannot put old heads on young shoulders” – You cannot expect young people to be as wise as elders. The Uzbek proverb “The old man knows what the fairy does not know” can be used instead of this proverb.

“Home lies the head that wears a crown”. The punishment for bigness.

From the Uzbek folk proverbs with the main lexeme “Until the fool has a head, be young for the wise”. In this proverb, the words fool-wise, head-young create a spiritual contradiction. The proverb reflects an instructive advice, and this is not a simple advice, but the entire content of this proverb enhances the essence and ensures that expressiveness and impact are even stronger. This proverb conveys the meaning of being young among some ignorant, unintelligent, uneducated, and ignorant people, rather than showing yourself to be their leader, that is, being inexperienced among people who are smarter than you and wiser than you, because there is no limit to knowledge, science, and enlightenment. Only fools think that they know everything. On the contrary, the more a person knows, the more he feels that he does not know.

CONCLUSION.

Proverbs are the result of the historical thoughts of a nation, which is called the “autobiographical” memory of a certain group. Proverbs are examples of national forms, harmoniously located in the consciousness of a nation and based on the national system of thinking. This naturally reflects the features of an ethnic group and is built as a result of genetic information. Therefore, many studies have been conducted on the universal and national characteristics of proverbs. If universal features are manifested in the structure, mono- and poly-spirituality, and themes of proverbs, the reason for this is historical development, the strengthening of international relations, and the growth of universal values. National features are a

reflection of the national character, the national spirit, and are characteristics belonging to a particular ethnic group. Without knowing the necessary aspects of a particular ethnic group, such as its place of residence, history, and nationality, it is absolutely impossible to understand the essence and meaning of its proverbs. Proverbs teach us to be vigilant, to distinguish a friend from an enemy, to be humane, kind, sweet-spoken, and loyal, to value parents, relatives, and friends, to respect elders, and to be compassionate toward younger ones. Therefore, it is appropriate to embellish our conversations with proverbs containing wise thoughts and use them effectively to instill our national cultural heritage in the minds of young people and to raise them as a well-rounded generation.

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